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Short Report

Novel Approach to QRS Complex Measurement in Left Bundle Branch Block

Abstract

Left Bundle Branch Block (LBBB) presents significant challenges in electrocardiogram (ECG) interpretation, particularly in accurately measuring the QRS complex. This paper presents a novel approach to QRS complex measurement in LBBB, developed by an experienced internist. The method addresses the limitations of both conventional manual techniques and automated ECG analysis systems when confronted with the complex morphology of LBBB.

QRS measurement in difficult cases

LBBB is characterized by a easy to detect widened ($>100\text{ms}$) QRS complex and altered ventricular depolarization pattern, which can obscure the typical landmarks used in ECG interpretation. This poses challenges in accurately determining the J-point and measuring the QRS duration, critical parameters in cardiac assessment. While automated ECG analysis has advanced significantly, it often falls short in complex cases like LBBB, necessitating manual interpretation by experienced clinicians.

The proposed approach consists of two complementary methods:

1. **QRS Tangent Method:** This technique involves manually extending the R/S wave upwards on the ECG printout using a ruler and pencil. The isoelectric line is then drawn, with the intersection point determining the J-point.

2. **T-wave Apex Method:** In cases where a subtle deflection from R/S to T-wave is discernible, a line is drawn from the apex of the T-wave to the lowest point of this deflection. This line may be extended further to intersect with the isoelectric line, providing an alternative J-point estimation.

These methods are applied in parallel, allowing for rapid assessment and cross-

validation. The approach essentially transposes the established tangent method from QT interval measurement to the QRS complex in LBBB

QRS Tangent Method

T-Wave Apex Method

Both figures show the QRS complexes plus the T wave of an electrocardiogram (ECG) of a patient with a left bundle branch block (LBBB)

The green line represents the electrical activity of the heart over time and shows the QRS complex followed by the T wave.

The red horizontal line represents the average isoelectric baseline. The blue vertical line intersects with the ECG curve at the point known as the J-point. Here: the transition of the QRS complex to the T wave. The black arrow points to this point and thus to the beginning of the T wave. These images represent our method for identifying the onset of the T wave during ECG analysis in LBBB. Determining the exact start of the T wave can be a challenge in this specific heart block, especially in cases with fine transitions from the ST segment to the T wave or even a fusion of QRS and T. So far, the results before all automatic analyses have been a weak point of this digital analysis. Our analog models (but in combination with the automated analysis) are a considerable help. Further studies on reliability in a larger patient group are recommended.

Discussion

The proposed methodology offers several advantages:

1. Adaptability: It can be tailored to various LBBB morphologies, addressing the high variability in these cases.
2. Practicality: The techniques are easily applicable in clinical settings, requiring only standard ECG equipment.
3. Complementarity: The use of two methods allows for cross-checking and increased confidence in measurements.
4. Bridge to Automated Analysis: This approach could inform improvements in automated ECG interpretation algorithms for complex LBBB cases.

However, limitations include the potential for inter-observer variability and the need for validation in larger studies.

Conclusion

This novel approach to QRS complex measurement in LBBB offers a practical solution to a persistent challenge in ECG interpretation. While further validation is

needed, it represents a promising step towards more accurate and reliable ECG analysis in complex cardiac conduction disorders.

Conflict of interests

None declared.

Sources

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